

**Food Trails of the Bengal Partition:
Studying Gastro-Politics in Bhaswati
Ghosh's Victory Colony 1950**

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The Partition of Bengal, a part of the great divide brought in through the larger Partition of India in 1947 along with the independence from the colonial British rule divided the land into two nation-states i.e., India and Pakistan. The province of Punjab in the west got bifurcated as roughly one half went to Pakistan and the other came to India on communal terms and similar interchange through the forced migration happened in the regions of Bengal, as the East Bengal became a part of Pakistan. It led to the influx of several prevalent notions

and divisions with mass migration that remain latent in the social consciousness and come out in varying ways. The bifurcation of the two territories that led to the divide of the shared spaces, histories and culture brought in waves of people with unfathomable experiences of people being killed, raped, mutilated and disposed off with the process of displacement. Again, a powerful blow came with another nationalist movement in 1971 when East Pakistan fought for its liberation from Pakistan on the grounds of differential cultural and linguistic identities that moved beyond the bounds of a shared religion. Following this, the amendment in the constitution of Bangladesh in 1977 to uphold a distinctive nationalism differing from the previous Bengali engagements further emphasized the breaking of any previous ties shared by the communities.

The sudden nationhood forced on the people hence created a phase of confusion and this uncertainty led to the crisis that the migrants or refugees felt with their existence and thus they tried to find several coping methods to stabilize their rootlessness. During this, the memories of regional delicacies along with the minimal belongings with which the people crossed the borders provided great comfort, and the influence of such food memories and seasonal rituals can still be found in the shared narratives. Food, for long, has been noted as an essential pillar for the building of habitual patterns and characteristics of a community as well as representing a compre-

hensive view towards the culture of a place along with its different movements. As the waves of people flooded into West Bengal from the borders, their culinary culture too migrated and got assimilated within the platter. Even though at a glance the food choices and cuisine seemed to be similar with the basic rice, dal, vegetable and fish, a deeper look into the ingredients and preparation methods presented the difference in the tastes as well as the identities infused with regionality and preferences. As social anthropologist Arjun Appadurai states, “food can be used to mark and create relations of equality, intimacy, solidarity or instead to uphold relations signalling rank, distance or segmentation” (Appadurai 1981).

The divide was noticed in the cultural sophistication presented by some elite sections of the natives as they looked down upon some of the ingredients preferred by the people from the eastern side. Kolkata then was a thriving port that imported all kinds of foreign ingredients and as Dhaka was comparatively less connected, the culinary choices were heavily influenced by the traditional and local ingredients that aided in the gastronomic habits and hence Kolkata’s prevalent food culture aggravated the feeling of the immigrant’s rootlessness even more. Though most of the condiments like certain greens and small fishes were almost a distant dream as they could not be found in the local markets even the taste of the familiar ingredients found here missed the freshness and the taste developed through the soil, water

and air which they once called their own. The hardships faced by these people in the various refugee camps such as food shortage or unsanitary living spaces, denial of the minimum necessities and further exploitation faced more severely by the people of lower classes made the longing for the homeland even more intense. The profound ways through which the trauma of displacement was experienced, moved beyond the class structures as every migrant of every economic stratum felt the loss of identity that the partition brought and was subtly channelled through the want of familiar food. The markets slowly started bringing in all kinds of ingredients, from *notay* (Amaranth), *kochu* (Taro), *paat* (Jute) *saag* (greens) to small fishes like *amodi* and *loita* (names of some fishes) along with *shutki maach* (sun-dried fermented fish), to meet the demands but the difference in the quality became a matter of bittersweet discontent.

Along with this, the women of the household tried to prepare items according to the traditional seasonal rites which they once followed and this adherence to the food customs presented a way of retaining their identity which they felt was going extinct. Hence, these differences brought in two different identities in the forced singular image of the Bengalis - the *Ghotis* (local people of West Bengal before Partition) and the *Bangals* (the East Bengali migrants). The difference between these two communities was stark, evident from several factors like dialect or even their preferred football teams, but

the taste preferences, condiments as well and preparations presented the direct picture. The *Ghotis* preferred lighter and more subtle tastes and ingredients like *posto* (poppy seeds) in their dishes which was appropriated through the colonial era at some points and even Vaishnavism which despised any pungency in their ingredients, with the kitchens being majorly under the control of the cooks. The *Bangals* on the other hand liked stronger and spicier dishes with a good amount of *morich baata* (chilli paste) which incorporated ingredients as varied as the multi-cultural population which stretched from Assam to Burma, involving different culinary styles. The distinction between the two communities also led to certain debates as in the earlier days the food choices of the *Bangals* were looked down upon by the *Ghotis* as noticed in the article "The Partitioning of Food": "West Bengal... was contemptuous on the unfamiliar East Bengali repertoire. How could turtle or pigeon meat be delicacies? Did civilized people eat snails heavy with garlic and mustard oil or eel roasted in bamboo stems?" (Sen, 2018). Similarly, the *Bangals* mocked the subtle taste preference of *Ghotis* as being stuck in the bygone era, of their colonial hangover.

The staunchness regarding the individuality of the culinary rituals by the *Bangals* increased even more after the Liberation War and the formation of Bangladesh to present a new identity to the landmass dominated by the Bengali Muslims and; the first thing to be discarded

was the previous food images as seen when the earlier *Dhakai Pulao* and the different fish preparations got replaced with the rise of the simple *Bhorta* and *Panta Bhaat* and the emergence of beef as the popular meat preference, thus almost erasing the shared culture of a community which was once its native. Hence, the debates over *Ilish Bhapa* (Steamed Hilsa fish with spices and oil) and *Chingri Malaikari* (Jumbo prawns in coconut gravy) marked not only the bittersweet rivalry among the Bangals and Ghotis, but it was also a desire for a community without an exclusive geographical territory which now existed only in their memories and was lived through their everyday practices. Thus, also presenting the politics of food in the simplistic art of consuming as noted in Arundhati Roy's words in her article "Food Prints of Partition": "...for it's the everyday nature of food that makes it so powerful in creating and nurturing a community's identity." (Roy, 2017)

The current paper will mainly focus on the different methods to equate food and identity and try to look at the bond between food and partition in different time spheres of colonial and post-colonial/post-partition phases. The shock of forced migration and later alienation based on unfamiliarity on foreign land and culture led to the core problems in representation to find one's place in the new home-land. The influx of people across the borders led to the introduction of several new ingredients to the existing cuisine and food culture. But

this influx of people and ingredients was not welcomed and was met with angst and disgust from the ‘bhadralok’ natives of the land. Thus, the politics of food in addition to the struggle to preserve a culture going through forced erasure during the post-independence developments through the culinary inheritance is investigated in this paper.

How does food provide a sense of belonging to a community of refugees by locating one to their region through nostalgia and through the longing for the native space of past existence? How does the material existence of food help to give life to an imaginary space? How does food act politically to help maintain one’s subjective identity even after drastic changes and movements in livelihood, belonging and national identity and thus also empower the resistance against generalization? These are some of the major questions this study aims to engage with. This paper hypothesizes that culinary habits act as an active force through its changes and adaptations to create a cultural space through the assimilation of the past within the present hence creating a community based on the roots living through their shared memories. Thus, this study aims to analyse the impact on the food culture of the Bengal region after Partition and the several actions associated with the changes in these everyday practices by critically approaching the novel *Victory Colony 1950* (2020) by Bhaswati Ghosh. Through the various modes of exploration, the exceptionality and the theoretical

engagement of food studies along with its concepts of communication and consumption will also be highlighted to bring in new dimensions and trajectories for approaching various themes.

Bhaswati Ghosh's debut novel *Victory Colony 1950* (2020) weaves a narrative in post-Partition Bengal drawing upon different themes addressing issues of communal riots, community faith, dividing class structures, gender politics, and nostalgia while keeping the displacement trauma felt at intra and interpersonal levels by the refugees along with the subtle images implying the *Bangal-Ghoti* divide. The story centres around an east Bengali migrant Amala Manna who survived the post-independence communal riots in 1949 and crosses the border with her brother Karthik, the only family member left to her. Soon after arriving on the platforms of Sealdah station, she finds her brother missing as she comes back empty-handed unable to find anything to feed him. Her bewilderment creates a ruckus for which the local policemen try to threaten her along with their crude advances but she is saved by Manas Dutta, a volunteer from the Gariahat Refugee Camp. Ghosh in her novel quite consciously presents the situations surrounding the refugee plight with a bit toned down extremity but, in her way, quite meticulously curates their life of deprivation along with disenfranchisement through the reference to food. The writer's self-acclaimed love for native food along with the thought of connecting with the roots is alluded to in

her interview with Madhushree Ghosh:

You know, as I was growing up in Delhi as a second-generation East Bengali refugee, I saw how food constituted the very grammar of displacement. It seemed to be the one tenuous link one could hold on to, albeit with compromises, to one's past. I remember the love with which my grandmother tried to recreate the flavours of her Barisal kitchen. When I wrote this book, food naturally became a marker, primarily of one's *desb* (native village) but also of the new palate to which the refugees had to adjust their taste buds to. (Ghosh 2021)

Earlier criticisms regarding the food connotations in the postcolonial narratives had often focused on the role of food as a signifier in constructing the composite national identity. As Sharmila Sen, in *Eating India: Literary and Cultural Consumptions of the Subcontinent* says, that most of such texts 'concerned with representing the culinary culture of a particular group to establish racial, ethnic, linguistic and national specificity' (Sen 2000); Similarly Mita Banerjee when addressing the 'chutney' metaphor in Salman Rushdie's *Midnight's Children*, stresses mostly on elaborating the blend of postmodern and postcolonial concepts as it expresses both the postcolonial cultural identity as well as the postmodern otherness as she warns against the notion of reduction of a culture to certain food items. But such readings often limit the multifaceted connotations regarding the food images as

noted in Henriette Heise's doctoral work titled *Food & Words* in 2012. Hence the current paper would attempt to read the various food references in the text with an attempt to analyse them for bringing in thoughts from multiple perspectives. The action of this novel is very much initiated with the food references as the novel almost begins with the core necessity of the survival struggle as the image of Karthik collapsing due to dire hunger and Amala meeting the absolute scathing face of the capitalistic metropolis, her new home as she collected a 'heap of scorn for daring to ask food without showing any money first' (Ghosh 2020, 3). The description of the surroundings is presented with food metaphors in an articulate way with the author stating that the station area looked like a 'fish market' to Amala or how the influx of the refugees in West Bengal was like 'pouring of sugar from torn sacks' where the refugees were often labelled as 'pests' (Ghosh 2020, 5) by the authorities as according to them the migrants infested the lands and brought in a certain kind of disruption to a set pattern hence creating a kind of turbulence in the body of the nation. The conversations here mostly get initiated with the sharing of food as at some point it acts as an icebreaker like the first friendly interaction which Manas had with Amala was through a packet of *muri* or puffed rice where she shared some information about her past or through the *kucho nimki* (fried flour snacks) at Chitra *massi's* house, or later it was over *muri makha* (puffed rice mixed roasted chick-peas, chopped coconut, green chillies, finely diced

onions, cucumber pieces and other condiments varying with individual choices). The references around food here again alluded to the cultures of urban and countryside spaces whereas on the other it brought in the class distinction which will be discussed later. Even when the incident about Minoti's rape was noted in Manas's diary the metaphor used in the description, 'A woman is the best piece of meat for all hungry men- rioters, criminals, political leaders' (Ghosh 2020, 58), the reduction of a woman's body to a food item with the site of consumption to bring out the violence and ravenousness of the situation not only presents the gender politics but also a sense of disgust.

The terrible living conditions and the psychological trauma that the refugees are subjected to, get even more critical in the text as the characters go through phases of eating disorders which have been noted to be one of the core symptoms in individuals who use it as a kind of coping mechanism to deal with their trauma as they may feel powerless after facing such an event and through such methods they try to conceal their emotions linked to desperation and fear. It is interesting to note how actions around Urmila and Moyna portray various techniques of modern therapy in simpler forms. First Urmila's situation was stabilized by comforting her through certain warm memories of food, for example, the *soru chakli* (thin rice-lentil crepes) making episode at Moyna's house (Ghosh 2020, 173). The nature of the different

relationships in the narrative is presented through the food references – the calming and loving feeling which Manas felt with his grandfather with a cup of tea, the sweet fights over various snacks or pieces of fish between the siblings Amala and Karthik or even the ease which Manas felt having a simple meal at Chitra Maasi's home which had the warmth he longed for but could not find in his mother's extravagant spread. The food item that has very much been associated with the refugees at the beginning of the novel is *Khichuri* or 'watery rice-lentil porridge'. The characteristics of this dish represent and at the same time defy certain notions. *Khichuri* in the very word holds the "bengaliness" as it stands different from 'Khichdi' in the other parts of India or porridge in the sense that dish mirrors the singular existence of the refugees and the hotchpotch situation due to the sudden mass migration. The adaptability of the refugees due to the changed circumstances very much resonated with this dish as it was easy to cook up with minimal ingredients. Such ingredients in this hotchpotch were almost the representation of the many various indigenous presences which were forced into a singular identity of being a Bengali of the Indian nation-state and to uphold the accumulated nationhood.

On the other hand, it also acted as a tool to present the 'othering' that these refugees faced of being reduced to mere burdened existences lacking any depth of identity or belonging as they are seen without any definition,

shape, structure or being formative like the bland *Khichuri*. But this fluid texture of *khichuri* also foretells some other ideas that are seen to be consolidated later with time. Nationalism stands to be the uniting force and the political principle propagated through ideologies and practices that supports the nation. Yet the measures that were taken in order to unify and balance the whole situation often presented a generalized narrative of the historical movement. This homogenisation excludes the nuances like that of the minute variations in details from the different groups of people within the communities of the refugees which might actually present a different understanding of unity when such differences are read. The refugees slightly deviated from the linear flow of thoughts associated to nationalism as in the process of reclamation of identity and the unity of these people stood on the concept of “ethnocultural distinctiveness” as marked by Rogers Brubaker in *Nationalism Reframed: Nationhood and National Question in the New Europe* (1996) and the anxieties related to such thoughts are well explained in Sumallya Mukhopadhyay’s thesis *From Rupture to Resilience: Memory and Identity in Oral Narratives of Refugees Arriving from the East Pakistan to West Bengal (1947-1970)*. As he states: “...the host nation is tormented by the presence of unknown persons. It brings about an ‘anxiety of incompleteness’ among the ruling elite of the country, and this feeling of incompleteness, does in turn, influence decisions concerning governance that can have detrimental effects on social, economic and po-

litical constitution of nation.” (Mukhopadhyay 2022, 17-18). Much like *Midnight's Children's* ‘chutney, the khichuri here is also very hard to contain and prone to leakage. Heise describes Rushdie's ‘chutney’ in the following way:

Saleem's idea of chutney – and by the parallel of the narrative – as representing completeness and as a possible container of the world is juxtaposed with postmodern imagery of leakage, spillage, of the pouring of emotions and memories into and out of people, of the continuing transformation even of chutney in jars” (Heise 2012, 157).

Likewise, Khichuri is known to be very adaptable. Owing to the compulsion of finding one's own space and identity the refugees spilt from the camps and with their former undefinable character and versatility newer hybrid identities were formed much like the *bhuna khichuri* (a variant of the porridge famous in the eastern region) later in *Victory Colony*. Hence, food here acts as a site of resistance as noted in the introductory chapter ‘Food Matters’ by Anita Mannur in her book *Culinary Fictions* (2009), while commenting on the role of food within the South Asian diasporic communities as being a medium for making certain aspects of these communities ‘palatable’ and how these foodways move through the lapse in the images of multiculturalism while questioning the extent of inclusivity:

“the ‘culinary’ most typically occupies a seemingly paradoxical space – at once a site of affirmation and

resistance. Affirmation, because food often serves to mark defining moments in marking the ethnicity of communities that live through and against the vagaries of diasporized realities, marred by racism and xenophobia. Resistance, insofar as the vocation of a culinary register can deliberately and strategically disrupt the notion that cultural identity is always readily available for consumption and commodification and always already conjoined to culinary practices.” (Mannur 2009, 8).

The resistance here is not to negate a consolidated Bengali identity but is against the various notions which sidelined the different variables that function within the structure and also the different layered identities which were yet to get recognition. The idea gets further explored as the simple yet elaborate meal prepared by Malati consisting of ‘mashed pumpkin served with a dash of oil, fried pumpkin peels and khesari dal, grass peas cooked in a thin, runny soup, and thick grains of rice malodorous with age’ (Ghosh 2020, 93) is presented as embodying the *Bangal* essence alongside the mention of the various *Ghoti* dishes like Manas’s favourite *luchi* with *alu-phulkopi chenchki* or ‘deep fried flour bread and potato-cauliflower stir-fry’ (Ghosh, 2020, p. 47) with a little tempering of *paanch phoron* or a kind of five spices. While many of the dishes are common in both the communities yet the difference in the preparation and taste preferences present the ambiguities and cracks that remain as the different strands of the New Bengali identity and food culture get intertwined.

Such differences in food dishes as well as their preparation further leads us to think about Bourdieu's theory of class distinction in this context. The notion is powered through the everyday action of food culture which acts mostly through the nature of taste and oral consumption. In the materialistic outlook towards society, Bourdieu views culture 'as capital, as social asset' (Moore, 2008) as it acts as the medium for construction as well as reproduction of social class. Therefore, taste, though being natural to human nature, in Bourdieu's view, it 'is an arbitrary construct and language of power' as 'meaning is assigned to specific choices of taste and opposed with meanings assigned to contrasting choices' (Heise 2012, 27). This factor of taste acts in the structure of one's thought process as it gets constructed under the influence of certain societal groups rather than being natural. Bourdieu's words elaborate this concept even more as he says:

One touches on the principle of the opposition between all rising classes, the bourgeoisie in an earlier period, now petite bourgeoisie, and the established classes, the aristocracy or the bourgeoisie. On the one hand, thrift, acquisition, accumulation, an appetite for possession inseparable from permanent anxiety about property, especially about women, the object of tyrannical jealousy which is the effect of insecurity; on the other, not only the ostentation, big spending and generosity which are some of the conditions for the reproduction of social capital, but

also self-assurance which is manifested, in particular, in aristocratic gallantry and elegant liberalism, forbidding the jealousy which treats the loved object as a possession – as if essential privilege conferred on the possessors of inherited wealth were freedom from the insecurity which haunts self-made men”. (Bourdieu 2010, 174-175)

This concept can be noticed in the episode describing Niranjan Chowdhury’s (a local zamindar whose land was acquired by the refugees and later developed to *Victory Colony*) way of spending the Kali puja evening where he and his coterie remains engrossed in card games, fine Scotch whiskey, hookah and Nautch girls while the womenfolk are focused on managing the actual puja. This was again accompanied by *bhog* (food offered to the Goddess) prepared by a special batch of *thakurs* (upper-caste cooks) without any trace of the succulent biriyani and goat curry by the *khansamah* (Muslim cooks) in a different kitchen (VC 1950, p. 84). The power politics behind the food behaviour here gets much more interesting through the dualism behind the thoughts as the patterns arising from a certain section stand in stark contrast to the food behaviour of another section. The financially uplifting ideals of liberalism attached to the zamindar can also be seen in the bringing together of food items which would be of great trouble if practised in the household of a lower-class family in the society. The zamindar’s food habits, conditioned through eco-

nomic and social lenses, frame his choice of freedom which is far distant from the ones which rise from the dire need associated with the simple yet functional meal prepared by Malati as it foregrounds the complex relationship between the dominant and the dominated, luxury and necessity.

The class complexities further get tangled through the episodes of sharing meals between the people of two social groups. When the idea of marriage between Amala and Manas got consolidated, the celebration took place in the form of Manas giving a pack of his beloved macaroons to Amala hence officially giving her a taste of the world he belonged to. But the kind of reaction Amala received from Mrinmoyee, her mother-in-law, evidently highlighted that Amala was not welcome to this elite social group. Mrinmoyee forced this exclusion very much by restricting Amala's entry to the kitchen or sharing a table with the family or later even denying her the same meals the other family members had and hence politicised the choice of food.

The metaphor gets further problematized through the purity-pollution politics as Amala's identity gets reduced several times through her economic class then through her caste origin (Namasudra) and finally through her refugee background. Here, Mrinmoyee is constructed as the relatively less modern orthodox Bhadramahila further presenting the power politics prevailing in the inner

workings of the household. Taking much pride in the aristocratic aura of the Dutta family, she mainly works her authority by retaining the domestic control with the kitchen being the main site of action and control. As she judges Amala's existence in the family, she declares to Haraprasad, her father-in-law, "I have no problem with that shudra girl staying in this house. Can't believe I'm being this kind. But Baba, with all due respect to you, I won't have that ugly Bangaal girl show up before people as Maanu's wedded wife" (Ghosh 2020, 229). She considered Amala to be a liability to the family's image and prestige and thus consolidated the kind of 'othering' Amala felt through rigid stares in both public and private spheres. The kind of insecurity Mrinmoyee felt with Amala's intrusion into the space she had wholeheartedly preserved is marked by Sarbani Banerjee in her thesis through the following assertion: "It is only by this 'motherly role' that a woman can at least temporarily tame the brash macho figure into a submissive son, through the promise of tender emotional dependence" (Banerjee 2015, 202). But this staunchness further made Manas decide to move out of the house marking a new journey where they made their own home with the first gifts from Chitra – a stove and kerosene to cook up newer tales – as the story ended with a fairy-tale ending involving Amala's reconciliation with her brother.

The novel revolves around the protagonist's struggle to reclaim identity with the complexity of rootlessness

in an unknown city, majorly focusing on the development of a community *Bijoy Nagar* or Victory Colony too. Along with Amala's tale, the presence of the narratives of the different refugee characters sharing common agonies and a sense of loss is the factor that provides a greater dimension for analysing the ideals of memory here. The community that gradually developed on the land through *jobordakhal* (forced accumulation) initially to survive in the alien land with dignity, almost attained a structure that followed an imaginary model of a land of their belonging which now remained solely in their memories. The food items grown in the surroundings of the colony, and the culinary patterns followed, almost trying to recreate the comforts they missed. The strangers in the camp gained a certain kind of control over their life finding a subjective identity as a sense of belonging grew along with the familial bonds after coming to the colony. The food here visibly remained as one of the most prominent forces that tied together the members through the acts of everyday sharing or communal cooking, social celebrations or seasonal rituals. But it is these food instances that again prove the notions around memory as argued by Santos mentioned earlier. The food here is often used to narrate the feelings that the refugees felt and their desire to be transported back to the times they longed for while sharing *muri-makha* (puffed rice mixture) or even the new restrictions associated with food items which the newly married Amala faced in contrast to the simple comforts around her

mother's fermented rice gruel or 'panta-bhaat with a few fritters or small fried fish'(Ghosh 2020, 229) in front of which the best meat and fish and other arrays of dishes at Manas's mansion seemed too sweet and unpalatable (Ghosh 2020, 252). Yet in the continued process of consumption, there is transformation and even if the sensory tool leads to remembrance of the experiences, the reproduction of the exact moments can never be possible as the identities formed have eventually gone through the process of hybridization. Heise emphasises the idea of "the impossibility of stability of meaning and narrative control: the nature of language already in process" (Heise 2012, 176) hinting at the impossibility around the recreation of experiences. Hence, the community here formed ultimately presents the experience of the past land even though cannot be brought back and concretized yet the process of formation of a new identity is hinted and it is this appetite that helps the community in its binding. Such a community stood as a part of the larger *Bangal* group with its layered hierarchies further complicated again by the taste as noted in the intra-communal politics hence presenting the dual nature of food which both divides as well unites in the broader context of a nation.

Through the gastronomic culture the difference between two communities, with now a common shared identity, tells a greater narrative with sensations as the culinary memories very much try to tell shared histories

of the struggle for the 'becoming' of this nation in its sumptuousness. In the critical study of the above text, food emerges as a subject that needs study beyond convention and the mere view of a literary device. It, in its organic form, moves around the stark realities of life which often stand in contrast to its nature. The object often looked forward to as the medium to curb hunger, in its multidimensional approach, triggers a kind of hunger that can never be satiated and is not even intended to do so. As such, ordinary everyday performances of food practices relatively bring forward a plethora of transdisciplinary questions which demand greater critical engagements and discussions.

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